

Implementation of Public Service Innovation Through the OK3S System (One Click Three Services) In the Muhammadiyah Sukabumi University Library

Alfa Robi^{1*}, Munandi Saleh², Rizki Hegia Sampurna³

Master of Administrative Sciences, University of Muhammadiyah Sukabumi, Indonesia

*Corresponding author: ar.alfarobi@gmail.com

Abstract

This research aims to find out how to implement public service innovation through the OK3S (One Click Three Services) system at the Muhammadiyah University Sukabumi Library. This study used a descriptive qualitative method. Data collection techniques using interviews, observation and document analysis. Data analysis techniques include data collection, data reduction, data presentation, and drawing conclusions. Research location at the Muhammadiyah University Sukabumi Library. The research results show (1) the Use dimension, the OK3S (One Click Three Services) system has provided convenience for users, namely final year students, (2) Performance, there has been an increase in the performance of Muhammadiyah University Sukabumi library employees, (3) User attitudes and beliefs, Implementation of the OK3S system innovation has a positive impact on feedback from stakeholders, especially final year students, lecturers and related stakeholders, (4) Integration into the organization (Integration into the organization) , the OK3S system is integrated with SIAK (Academic and Financial Information System) so that students only need to use the email as recorded in SIAK to access OK3S, (5) Effectiveness of implementation effort (Effectiveness of implementation efforts) in its implementation has passed the preparation, system development, and implementation of the system. However, in practice, implementation is not optimal due to several obstacles encountered.

Keywords: implementation of innovation, public services, OK3S System.

Introduction

In general, public services refer to a series of activities carried out by government agencies or institutions and the private sector with the aim of meeting community needs. Public services are regulated by law, such as Law Number 25 of 2009 in Indonesia, which establishes the framework and obligations for public service providers. The aim is to ensure that every citizen and resident has equal access to necessary goods, services and administrative services. In this context, public service is an obligation that must be fulfilled by organizers, both in the government and private sectors, in order to support the needs and interests of the community in accordance with applicable regulations. According to Santosa (2008:57), public service is the provision of services, either by the government, the private sector on behalf of the government,

or the private sector to the community, with or without payment to meet the needs and/or interests of the community. This underscores the importance of transparency, accountability and equality in the provision of public services to all individuals in need.

In the world of education, especially universities, they can be seen as service or service providers, while students are considered as service or service users. Educational institutions, especially universities, offer a wide range of services. The main services provided are usually learning or academic services, but other services such as academic administration services, consultation/guidance, libraries, laboratories, internet/computers, canteens, research, sports facilities, etc. are also an inseparable part of the service. public in Higher Education.

It cannot be denied that every agency or higher education institution will carry out service provision as one of the main tasks for the smooth running of various existing activities. This is also what the best university in the city and district of Sukabumi is trying to achieve according to the EduRank 2023 version, namely the Sukabumi Muhammadiyah University (UMMI). Muhammadiyah University Sukabumi (UMMI) always tries to provide the best service in meeting all student needs, with the hope that students will feel satisfied because good service can also create a positive image for the institution. One of the public services provided by Muhammadiyah University Sukabumi (UMMI) is the service carried out by the Library Technical Implementation Unit (UPT).

Based on the government regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 24 of 2014 concerning the implementation of Law Number 43 of 2007 concerning Libraries, it is explained that a university library is a technical implementation unit (UPT) which is an integral part of education, research and community service activities and functions as learning resource center to support the achievement of educational goals based in higher education. The existence of a library is able to meet the information needs of all academics in the university environment.

Libraries in supporting education in tertiary institutions must also be able to carry out their role optimally. Libraries play a role in the process of selecting, collecting, processing, maintaining and providing information to the entire academic community. In accordance with what Saleh (1995: 17) said, the university library plays a role as one of the academic center equipment units in supporting the dharma of education and teaching, so that for this reason the library collects, processes, provides and disseminates information in accordance with curriculum in universities. Libraries have a strategic role in providing access to information, supporting learning and developing knowledge. In accordance with the Vision of the Muhammadiyah University of Sukabumi (UMMI) Library, namely to make a superior library as a center for information services and knowledge sources in supporting Catur Dharma, Muhammadiyah University of Sukabumi. Muhammadiyah Sukabumi University's efforts to provide and improve the best services for student satisfaction must pay attention to student needs and desires, one of which is provided by services from the Sukabumi Muhammadiyah University (UMMI) Library.

During the Covid-19 pandemic, due to limited access to the library, the Muhammadiyah Sukabumi University (UMMI) library prepared a link to access several services for final year students including free library services, plagiarism verification services and KTI (Scientific Writing) submission services by utilizing G-form (Google Forms) and email facilities. Because

this service produces a free UMMI library card which is one of the requirements for graduation registration. During Covid-19, officers experienced difficulties when serving users online. This happened because the service conditions experienced very high queues during graduation registration. In providing these services, library staff experience problems when providing services manually with user needs that demand to be resolved immediately. This condition continues to recur with various problems, namely speed, accuracy and communication in services which give rise to complaints from students, lecturers and study programs who consider library services to be considered slow. Based on UMMI e-complaint data, which is a medium for submitting complaints to service providers with the aim of improving the quality of service at Muhammadiyah University Sukabumi. That in 2019 and 2020 there were complaints from students regarding plagiarism checking services. (a) There are many complaints from final year students, both those who are still preparing their thesis or those who have carried out their thesis exams, regarding the services provided by the UMMI library regarding turnitin checks which we feel are inefficient and too complicated and take too long, (b) My complaint about the performance process of library staff is that it takes a very long time to respond, in our SIAK (Academic Information System) there are graduation requirements regarding plagiarism checking, the plagiarism-free letter has been signed by the supervisor. However, the SKPP (Plagiarism Checking Certificate) did not come out straight away, whereas in the graduation requirements, there was an attachment that required this action.

Even though in these services, the UMMI Library has optimized HR (Human Resources) to increase service time, it does not provide the best solution because these various services still carry out a long process in each service. Some of the problems faced relate to speed and accuracy as well as communication in services. This problem arises because the provision of services is still done manually, namely via Google Form with several access links so that officers have to check the incoming applications one by one. Officers also have to write letters manually, which is quite time consuming. Communication with users is also less effective because it is done via email which often causes spam. The UMMI Library continues to make improvements to the service system, which in 2021 will analyze data on system requirements and input from users, library staff, leaders and various parties. Based on these conditions, the UMMI library carried out an innovative transformation of library services by combining three services, namely: free library services, plagiarism verification services and Scientific Writing (KTI) submission services using one system called the OK3S (One Click Three Services) system. The OK3S system was launched in June 2022 and was used for the first time for students registering for graduation in October 2022. The OK3S system has been running for 2 graduation periods, namely wave I in October 2022 and wave II in March 2023. Library UMMI has conducted a user satisfaction survey of the OK3S system to see to what extent this system is useful for meeting the needs of users, especially final year students. The survey was conducted at the UMMI Library using Google Form to fill in the questionnaire. The total number of respondents was 77, taken randomly with the criteria of representing OK3S system users consisting of final year students and UMMI alumni. The survey results show that user satisfaction with using the OK3S system is relatively high, as evidenced by the relatively high satisfaction index reaching 80%.

However, the OK3S system is crucial because it ensures that students receive optimal service, and based on the survey above, it is clear that with the OK3S system, users feel satisfaction because of the ease of accessing library services, although there are still 20% who do not feel satisfied. Thus, the implementation of the OK3S system is not only an innovation, but also an important basis for efficiency and comfort in service. This is a positive phenomenon that is interesting to research. Based on the opinion of Sekaran and Bougie (2016:33) stated:

“A 'problem' does not necessarily mean that something is seriously wrong with a current situation that needs to be rectified immediately. A problem could also indicate an interest in an issue where finding the right answers might help to improve an existing situation. Thus, it is fruitful to define a problem as any situation where a gap exists between the actual and the desired ideal states.”

According to Sekaran and Bougie (2016:33), research does not always raise negative issues, but also things that attract attention because they are positive. If a negative phenomenon is being studied, the aim is to find a solution or help improve it so that it does not get worse. On the other hand, if research raises positive things, it is intended to help people continue to improve and provide lessons to others. Although based on the survey results, it shows that there is a positive phenomenon because it reaches 80% which is included in the satisfied category, according to researchers there is still a need for research to find out the 20% dissatisfaction with this public service innovation.

From the background of the problems described previously, this research proposes a problem formulation, namely, how is the implementation of public service innovation through the OK3S (One Click Three Services) system in the Muhammadiyah University Sukabumi Library?

Definition of Public Service

Public services are activities or series of activities in order to fulfill service needs in accordance with statutory regulations for every citizen and resident regarding goods, services and/or administrative services provided by public service providers. Public service providers are every state administration institution, corporation, independent institution formed based on law for public service activities, and other legal entities formed solely for public service activities. Loss of public trust in public service providers will result in damage to the legal order and regulations which are a prerequisite for state sovereignty. Regulations and order are the basic capital for building democracy and justice in society. (Sellang, 2016)

OK3S system Service Innovation Program (One Click Three Services)

OK3S (One Click Three Services) is an integrated UMMI library service aimed at final year students at Sukabumi Muhammadiyah University (UMMI). This innovative system aims to integrate three main services in one easily accessible platform. OK3S offers integrated services that include library-free processes, plagiarism verification, and submission of scientific papers for final year students at Muhammadiyah University Sukabumi. The main aim of this service is to facilitate students in obtaining a Library Free Card which is one of the graduation

requirements. Through OK3S, students can carry out library-free processes, plagiarism verification and submit scientific papers (KTI) for both students in the general (regular) final assignment category and special final assignment categories.

a) Library Free

Library exemption is a letter stating that the student concerned does not have any responsibility for collection loans or fines at the Muhammadiyah University Sukabumi Library. Every Muhammadiyah University Sukabumi student who has completed their studies and will register for graduation is required to attach a Library Free as one of the prerequisites.

b) Plagiarism Verification

Plagiarism Verification is an examination carried out to ensure the correctness of documents, data or information produced by students' written work. By ensuring that there are no ethical and copyright violations in the form of exploiting or using other people's work without permission from the original owner/creator and making it as if they were their own work.

c) Scientific papers

Scientific work is written work created using scientific principles based on data and facts obtained from observations, experiments and literature studies. Scientific writing can be in the form of a thesis, thesis or journal, which is mandatory for students to complete as a final requirement for graduation.

Framework of Thinking

A framework is a construction of thought used by researchers to overcome the problems faced, by utilizing theories that are relevant to the focus of the research. In this research, the focus is the implementation of public service innovation through the OK3S (One Click Three Services) system at the Muhammadiyah University Sukabumi Library. The researcher concludes that Real and Poole's Theory of Measuring the Success of Innovation Implementation (2005: 73) is a relevant framework for answering this research problem.

Based on this theory, there are five variables that influence the successful implementation of innovation, namely:

- a. Use
- b. Performance (Performance)
- c. User Attitudes and Beliefs
- d. Integration into the Organization (Integration into the Organization)
- e. Effectiveness of Implementation Effort

By referring to the factors mentioned by Real and Poole (2005), researchers will use these five indicators to assess the success of innovation implementation in their research on the Implementation of Public Service Innovation through the OK3S System in the Muhammadiyah University Sukabumi Library.

Figure 1. Thinking Framework

Method

Object of research

The object of this research is students who experience the OK3S (One Click Three Services) system at the Muhammadiyah University Sukabumi Library. Implementation of Public Service Innovation through the OK3S (One Click Three Services) System at the Muhammadiyah University Sukabumi Library. This research focuses on the Implementation of Public Service Innovations, so the focus of attention is on the OK3S (One Click Three Services) system at the Muhammadiyah University Sukabumi Library because it is the main target of this research. This research needs to be analyzed and researched further in an effort to optimize the Muhammadiyah University of Sukabumi Library Services to make them even better. For the research location, researchers will conduct research directly at the Sukabumi Muhammadiyah University Library. By visiting these locations, it is hoped that you will get more accurate and reliable data.

Research methods

The researcher chose a qualitative research method with the aim of making the results obtained more comprehensive so that the data collected reflects the reality of the field. In the data collection process, researchers prioritize the views of the data source rather than personal views. Based on these considerations, the researcher chose to use a qualitative research method with a descriptive approach, because the data produced is in the form of writing, words and descriptive documents from reliable sources or informants.

Research Design

The data collection technique applied in this research follows a qualitative approach, namely, Observation is a data collection technique that is carried out by direct observation of the object to be studied. Then Interview, namely the researcher interacts directly with the informant to obtain the necessary information. Interviews involve the interviewer asking questions and the interviewee providing answers. And finally, Documents, the use of written documents as a

method of collecting qualitative data. Researchers collect relevant documents to explain the phenomena in the research. In this research, the documents used are instructions or procedures related to the Implementation of Public Service Innovations through the OK3S (One Click Three Services) System at the Muhammadiyah University Sukabumi Library. To determine informants, researchers used a purposive method, where the selection of informants was based on certain criteria that were relevant to the information required. Informants were selected based on their expertise or knowledge of the OK3S (One Click Three Services) System. The informant in this research was the Muhammadiyah University Sukabumi Library Manager. To ensure the validity of the data and gain in-depth understanding, researchers also selected the Head of the Management Information Systems Technical Implementation Unit (UPT SIM) Muhammadiyah University of Sukabumi as the OK3S system creator and students as system users. The following is a list of informants who have agreed to be interviewed:

Table 1. Informant Data

Informant Code	Informant's Name	Information
Informant 1	Yanti Sundari, S. Sos., MIKom.	Head of UPT. Muhammadiyah Sukabumi University Library as system manager OK3S (One Click Three Services)
Informant 2	Yonan Bastiar, ST, M.Si	Head of UPT. SIM Muhammadiyah University Sukabumi as developer of the OK3S (One Click Three Services) system
Informant 3	Bobor Oktora, S.AP.	Staff of the Institute for Research and Community Service (LPPM) Muhammadiyah University of Sukabumi as Plagiarism Validation Verifiers for the OK3S (One Click Three Services) system
Informant 4	Sani Zulviah, S.Kom	Services Division Information and communication technology UPT. Muhammadiyah University Sukabumi Library as OK3S (One Click Three Services) system operator
Informant 5	Fuji Amalia Conscience, SIPust.	UPT Technical Services Division. Muhammadiyah University Sukabumi Library as Verifier of Scientific Writing for the OK3S system (One Click Three Services)
Informant 6	Syifa, SIPust.	UPT User Services Division. Muhammadiyah University Sukabumi Library as Verifier of Scientific Writing for the OK3S system (One Click Three Services)

Informant 7	Muhammad Akbar Maulana	Muhammadiyah University Sukabumi Students as Users of the OK3S (One Click Three Services) system
Informant 8	Ahmad Sayuti	Muhammadiyah University Sukabumi Students as Users of the OK3S (One Click Three Services) system

Source: processed by researchers (2024)

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Analysis of data and results of field research carried out by researchers using the Innovation Implementation model of Real and Poole theory, namely; Use, Performance, User Attitudes and Beliefs, Integration into the Organization, Effectiveness of Implementation Effort. Here is the explanation:

1. Use

To try to capture the extent to which innovations are actually used in practice, it is important to know the uses and benefits of those innovations. According to Leonard-Barton quoted by Real and Poole (2005: 76), one indicator of the success of implementing an innovation is the use of the innovation. Apart from that, several measures also focus on the completeness and sophistication of this innovation in providing convenience to users.

a) Before the system existed OK3S (One Click Three Services).

During the graduation registration period at Muhammadiyah University of Sukabumi, there are requirements that must be completed, namely obtaining a Library Free Card (SKBP) in accordance with academic guidelines so that there are process stages that final year students must go through, namely the Library Free service, Plagiarism Verification service and submission service Scientific papers.

Free library service is a service provided by the Muhammadiyah Sukabumi University Library to final year students as a graduation requirement to obtain a letter stating that the student concerned does not have collection loan responsibilities or fines at the Muhammadiyah Sukabumi University Library. Every Muhammadiyah University Sukabumi student who has completed their studies and will register for graduation is required to attach a Library Free as one of the prerequisites.

Meanwhile, the Plagiarism Verification service is a service provided to students during examinations carried out to ensure the correctness of documents, data or information resulting from student written work. By ensuring that there are no ethical and copyright violations in the form of exploiting or using other people's work without permission from the original owner/creator and making it as if they were their own work.

And the Scientific Writing submission service is a service for submitting written work created using scientific principles based on data and facts obtained from observations, experiments and literature studies. Scientific writing can be in the form of a thesis, thesis

or journal, which is mandatory for students to complete as a final requirement for graduation. Based on the results of the interview revealed by N.5 at the Muhammadiyah University Sukabumi Library on Monday, 03 June 2024 at 13.00 WIB. He stated that:

"Before the OK3S system existed, students were required to submit scientific papers, verify plagiarism and provide free library services through several links that we provided. "The link is separate and also connected to the UMMI library Gmail."

Based on these interviews and based on observations made by researchers, the service links created by the Sukabumi Muhammadiyah University Library consist of three service links. Library free link (<https://bit.ly/Layananbebaspustaka>), Turnitin Plagiarism Verification (<https://bit.ly/VerifikasiPlagiarism>), And Independent KTI Collection (<https://bit.ly/LayananPenerimaanKti>). *Link* It utilizes G-form (Google Form) and email facilities. So, students must enter each link from the three free library services, verify plagiarism and submit scientific papers. Meanwhile, officers need to check every incoming email and then process them one by one.

b) After the OK3S system (One Click Three Services).

By using this link, library staff experience problems when providing services, because it is done manually while student needs must be resolved immediately. This condition continues to recur with various problems, namely speed, accuracy and communication in services which give rise to complaints from students, lecturers and study programs who consider library services to be considered slow. Even though in terms of service, the library has optimized HR (Human Resources) to increase service time, it does not provide the best solution because these various services still carry out long processes in each service, especially plagiarism verification services. This process takes quite a long time and cannot be done in a hurry, even though there are many queues of incoming files, it still has to be done carefully. From these conditions, one access is needed to provide three services; library free, plagiarism verification and submission of scientific papers. Based on the results of an interview delivered by N.1 at the Muhammadiyah University Sukabumi Library on Monday, 03 June 2024 at 10.00 WIB. He stated that:

"OK3S is an abbreviation for One Click Three Services which is a library innovation which is an integrated library service to get a free library card which will later be a requirement for Graduation registration. "The aim of creating the OK3S system is to help final year students fulfill their obligations in collecting scientific papers, free library services and plagiarism verification in one service platform."

From the results of the interview, the researcher concluded that OK3S (One Click Three Services) is an innovation carried out by the Sukabumi Muhammadiyah University Library which aims to help final year students get a Library Free Card which is a requirement for Graduation registration. Meanwhile, regarding the completeness and sophistication features of the OK3S (One Click Three Services) system, based on an interview with N.4 who was interviewed by researchers at the Sukabumi Muhammadiyah University Library on June 6 2024, it was stated that there are features in the OK3S (One Click Three Services) system, namely:

“OK3S can be opened by typing the ok3s link or opening the UMMI library website. There are features in the OK3S system, namely free library service features, plagiarism verification services, and free library collection services. On the first page you will be shown a page for logging in which can be opened with a SIAK account or Google account, then after logging in you will be shown the home page, services, profile and guide”

Figure 2. View of the UMMI Library page

Based on the results of the interview and based on the OK3S (One Click Three Services) guidebook, the completeness and sophistication features of the OK3S (One Click Three Services) system will be explained below:

c) Home Page

On the OK3S home page, students have access to several available menus, namely Home, Services (Library Free, Plagiarism Verification, and KTI), Library Free Card, Guide, and Profile.

Figure 3. Home page

- Home: This menu directs students back to the OK3S student home page. When you

first access OK3S, students receive information about having to complete their profile data. Students are required to complete a profile first. If the profile has not been completed, when students try to access the available menu, OK3S will display a page asking them to complete the profile before continuing. This aims to ensure that student data is recorded completely.

- Services: This menu provides access to the available services, namely Library Free, Plagiarism Verification, and KTI. In the service menu, students are allowed to start by selecting the free library or plagiarism verification menu without having to wait for a service to complete first. However, to access the KTI menu, the plagiarism verification process must be completed first, because the authenticity of scientific work must be validated before students can upload KTI into the OK3S system.
- Library Free Card: This menu provides access to the Library Free Card creation process page. A library free card can be obtained if you have completed the library free process, plagiarism verification and KTI submission.
- Guide: This menu provides access to the download page for the "OK3S Usage Guide" on the UMMI library website.
- Profile: This menu allows students to view and edit academic profile data in the form of personal information and supervisor profiles.

Based on the explanation above, the Sukabumi Muhammadiyah University Library has experienced a significant transformation in public services. Initially, their services were often considered troublesome and they often received complaints because they used Google form links and emails in the library-free service process, plagiarism verification, and submission of scientific papers which made the process more complicated. However, through the innovation of the OK3S (One Click Three Services) system, the library has succeeded in creating a solution that integrates these three services into one easily accessible access. The features provided in the OK3S system are designed efficiently according to their respective functions, so that nothing is wasted.

2. Performance (Performance)

Innovation is often applied to improve various aspects of organizational performance, so that performance becomes a relevant success criterion. According to Real and Poole (2005: 77) citing Grover, Jeong, Kettinger, and Teng, suggesting that to assess innovation performance, the main attention should be focused on three aspects: cost reduction, time reduction, and reduction of document errors. To identify changes in employee performance whether there are significant changes, it is necessary to first know the conditions before this OK3S innovation. So, the researcher tried to interview OK3S managers and summarized them:

a) Before OK3S (One Click Three Services)

Based on an interview with N.5 on June 3 2024 at 13.00 at the Sukabumi Muhammadiyah University Library, he stated that:

"Officers experienced many obstacles before OK3S existed, because each service was carried out separately and took more time and effort. "Because when collecting free library

services, plagiarism and scientific papers are done using email and must be checked one by one."

Also supported by statement N.3 on June 6 2024 at 09.00 in the LPPM room (Research institutions and community service) Muhammadiyah University of Sukabumi stated: "Plagiarism verification is a process that takes time and energy, so it requires a solution that is able to overcome speed and accuracy constraints." During the graduation registration period, there are requirements that must be completed, namely obtaining a library free card in accordance with academic guidelines so that there are process stages that final year students must go through, however there are obstacles felt by the officers. Based on the results of the interview, the researcher summarized the following:

- Library Free

In the free library service, students no longer have book loans, have completed the administration fees and if the student is a member of the Sukabumi City Regional Library and Archives Service (Dispusipda) and/or the Sukabumi Regency Archives and Library Service (Diarpus) they are required to attach a free library letter from related agencies. From these several things, the need arises for students who always ask officers about borrowing books, the administration fee process and also library exemption letters from related agencies, making students confused and feeling that the process takes too long to obtain a library exemption letter.

- Plagiarism verification

Plagiarism verification service that must be in sync with LPPM's plagiarism SOP (Research institutions and community service)UMMI, which includes an SKBP (Library Free Certificate) given to final year students, after verification of plagiarism in the library, students bring a certificate of plagiarism checking from the library to LPPM (Research institutions and community service). After that, the LPPM officer creates an SKBP and it is received by the students via email. This letter was written by LPPM, causing students to wait a long time for the completion process until they received the SKBP and entered the stage of submitting scientific work at the library. The queue is considered long by students by calculating the processing time until the letter from LPPM, even though the bureaucracy is different, is still considered part of the plagiarism verification service in the library. This has caused the image of the UMMI library to decline because it is considered a long bureaucratic process.

- Free Submission of Literature

There is a different perception when students make free handovers of libraries because the officers convey a shortage of files via email, so students sometimes open emails or use emails that are rarely opened or forget passwords. Students often ask officers about the progress of completing scientific work. Communication between students and officers is felt to be less effective, so sometimes students convey their complaints to the head of the study program or their supervisor. Then the head of the study program or lecturer conveys his complaint to the head of the library.

Apart from that, during the graduation registration period, students who have graduated at the same time go to the library to provide services to get a library free card. Meanwhile, there are still limited human resources in the UMMI library, so that every graduation registration period, 7 library staff are deployed to speed up the completion of the service process and increase service time until there are overtime hours when serving final year students. As stated by N.6 on 04 June 2024 at 11.30 at the Muhammadiyah University Sukabumi Library: "Before OK3S existed, queues were often huge because officers had difficulty handling students one by one. In fact, we often ask other officers to help but it is still not handled well, so the service becomes slow."

Complaints made by students, lecturers and even study programs that they feel slow in handling this service create a level of stress for library staff. And the limited conditions of equipment and work equipment during the Covid-19 era created obstacles for officers to maximize services. Even though officers have tried to divide up their work because they still use a manual system, the work is still overwhelming.

There are letters that are requested repeatedly by students because the procedures applied in each study program are different, such as the trial requirements requiring a plagiarism checking letter, at the time of the trial there were those who required library-free when registering for graduation, these requirements were requested again by the faculty, so that there were officers who had to work. repetition is carried out, even though the file is stored on the officer's computer, it takes time to complete the service. The free library payment report data, which requires proof of student payment to be attached when submitting a budget, becomes a problem during the budget disbursement process because it goes into the university account which is mixed up with the same costs in that account, so officers need time to summarize the report.

The officer's analysis of membership with collaboration partners, namely the Sukabumi City Regional Library and Archives Service (Dispusipda) and/or the Sukabumi Regency Archives and Library Service (Diarpus), because officers need to ensure that UMMI students who are members of the library no longer have any loans. The plagiarism verification service must be in sync with the plagiarism SOP from LPPM UMMI, which includes a letter given to final year students who have verified plagiarism in the library.

Another problem occurs when the plagiarism check carried out by the supervising lecturer is verified in the library, then there are findings of "cheating" so it takes time to convey the findings to the supervising lecturer by looking for the lecturer's contact. During Covid 19, the UMMI library took steps to change the regulations regarding the submission of scientific papers which were previously printed as soft files. This is in accordance with the leadership's direction to change the UMMI library towards a digital library that is able to facilitate academics online. The suitability of scientific work files submitted at the time of submission to the library must comply with the provisions of the Ministry of Education and Culture's RAMA repository, so that scientific papers uploaded to the repository have been checked first in the scientific paper submission service section so officers need to be careful in checking

scientific papers, especially those related to applicable provisions so that there is no double publication.

The system queue is considered long, students think that the time calculated from the start of uploading is calculated even though the library service is closed, so thinking that this time is long gives rise to misperceptions about library regulations. Limited communication often occurs between students and officers, even though they are assisted by the library hotline, students tend to ask the library hotline repeatedly so that services are hampered because they are required to check and answer students' questions.

b) After the OK3S (One Click Three Services) system

To find out the management performance of the OK3S (One Click Three Services) innovation, researchers conducted interviews with officers who served as verifiers for each free library service, plagiarism verification and scientific paper submission services. The results of the interviews will be outlined in two aspects, namely the impact to improving performance for librarians and increasing appreciation for librarians.

From the results of interviews conducted with two librarians and one LPPM staff who served as verifiers for each free library service, plagiarism verification and scientific paper submission service, it was agreed that the OK3S (One Click Three Services) innovation which unites these three services has had a positive impact. for several aspects including:

- Effectiveness and efficiency of service delivery.

Previously, each of the library-free services, plagiarism verification and scientific paper submission services were provided manually with a process that was quite time consuming, causing long queues because they had to check the applications one by one on the Google form, communication was carried out only via email, which was less effective. because users often do not check incoming emails and sometimes this results in email spam, so many complaints come in from users either directly to the librarian's personal number or via the library hotline regarding the length of the verification process due to the long queue and also the stages which are quite long and can be said to be complicated for the user. some users. Using OK3S makes the process of serving these three services effective and efficient because the three services have been combined in one system and not through several access links, communication can be carried out in the system, making it easier for librarians and users to monitor the progress of each of these services. According to the statement from N.6 on 04 June 2024 which stated that:

"After the OK3S system was introduced, everything has become one door, which was previously separate and troublesome, but is now more effective and efficient.

"Apart from that, if there is something you feel is missing or you want to ask, you can submit it directly via the notes feature in the OK3S system."

- Services become orderly administration

The OK3S system innovation makes the service more orderly in administration, because officers no longer need to create letters manually because they can be

generated by the system, making it easier for officers to tidy up administrative correspondence. Not only that, for self-service reporting which was previously done manually using Ms. Excel, now reports can be exported from the system and officers only need to tidy them up. Based on what was conveyed by N.5 on 04 June 2024, it stated that:

"In sending documents, there were often formatting errors from students. Before OK3S existed, sometimes some were often revised but were still wrong, so students were disappointed. However, after the OK3S system was introduced, the letter format just had to be taken from the system and students just needed to adjust it."

- Improved performance of librarians

The use of the OK3S system has a significant impact on the performance of librarians, where librarians who serve as verifiers when approaching graduation are usually busy only providing free library services, plagiarism verification and scientific paper submission services which are very time consuming so that sometimes a lot of other work is delayed. As the graduation day approaches, many users apply for services and add more queues, so it is not uncommon for several additional officers to handle each of these services, but currently only one officer is enough to focus on handling one service so that it no longer interferes with the completion of other work because Some jobs that are usually done manually can be replaced using the system. According to the statement from N.6 on 04 June 2024 which stated that:

"Towards graduation, officers are often busy, causing other work to be neglected, but OK3S can make it easier for officers to complete their duties in serving final year students and can continue their other work."

3. User Attitudes and Beliefs

User attitudes and beliefs are also important factors in the successful implementation of an innovation, according to Real and Poole (2005: 77). When organizational members have positive attitudes and beliefs towards the innovation, the likelihood of its benefits being realized is greater because the impact of the innovation is highly dependent on the level of user involvement. On the other hand, innovations that have been proven to be useful and implemented well tend to strengthen positive attitudes and beliefs.

The innovation of the OK3S system certainly influences feedback from stakeholders. With this system, the performance of librarians in providing services is well appreciated, especially by final year students, lecturers and other relevant stakeholders. If you look at the use of OK3S, many complaints came from students because the free library service process, plagiarism verification and scientific paper submission services were felt to take quite a long time. Not only from students but also from several parties such as supervisors who also received this news from the students, they supervised so they submitted complaints to the library. Based on UMMI e-complaint data, before the OK3S system existed, the UMMI Library received complaints from students regarding services.

"There have been many complaints from final year students, both those who are still preparing their thesis or those who have carried out their thesis exams, regarding the services provided by the UMMI library regarding turnitin checks, which we feel are inefficient and too complicated and therefore take too long."

"My complaint is about the performance process of library staff which takes a very long time to respond, in our SIAK (Academic Information System) there are graduation requirements regarding plagiarism checking, the plagiarism-free letter has been signed by the supervisor. "However, the SKPP (Plagiarism Checking Certificate) does not continue to come out, whereas in the graduation requirements, there is an attachment that requires this action" (Library E-Complaint Recapitulation Results, 2020).

After using OK3S, there were many fewer complaints and more positive feedback was received by library staff. The OK3S system is still relatively new but its impact has been felt by final year students, lecturers and library staff as verifiers. The good responses conveyed by users or users of the OK3S system were related to the effectiveness and efficiency of the OK3S system which makes the entire service process for final year students easier, clearer and faster. In accordance with the statement from N.7 on June 3 2024 at 14.00, namely that:

"OK3S is very important because before graduation, students are required to collect free libraries, scientific papers and plagiarism. With OK3S, it is able to make it easier for students to submit assignments. The system is easy and simple to use because there are not many features in it, there are only features for collecting the three services, student profiles and there are also guidelines for their use. Apart from that, the collection is also very fast, only a few minutes. And the problem is that it often cannot be accessed because the network is not good."

Based on these interviews, it is proven that the OK3S system can help make it easier for final year students to complete their obligations. However, even so, there are still obstacles experienced by some students because they don't know the information about OK3S. As stated by N.8 on June 5, 2024, at 13.00 which stated that:

"I have tried the OK3S system and thank God it is very easy once you understand it, but unfortunately the OK3S system is often inaccessible. Apart from that, it wasn't publicized beforehand, especially to postgraduate students, I also heard about it from friends. So in my opinion it would be good to socialize this system to final year students beforehand. Apart from that, if possible, the system will add a video tutorial, so you don't have to bother reading the guide."

This statement explains that there is still a need for outreach to final year students by the library management regarding the OK3S system because there are still those who have not received guidance regarding the OK3S system.

4. Integration into the organization (Integration into the organization)

Integration into an organization is also a marker of the success of an innovation, according to Real and Poole (2005: 78). In addition, Iacovou, Benbasat, and Dexter (1995), as mentioned in Real and Poole (2005: 79), highlight another indicator that the level of

innovation integration can be measured by how well the innovation is integrated with other systems.

OK3S was developed with a collaborative system from various parties. Based on the results of the interview with N.1 on June 9 2024 at 16.00, the researcher then summarizes. Whereas initially the Head of the Muhammadiyah Sukabumi University library held discussions with lecturers in the UMMI Informatics Engineering study program regarding the system requirements needed in the library and it was recommended that students of the Muhammadiyah Sukabumi University Informatics Engineering study program undertake internships/Field Work Practices (PKL) with their abilities/skills. can create such a system. After administratively submitting the PKL internship letter and receiving a response to the internship letter, the library and PKL students carry out an analysis of the system required by the library.

The head of the library becomes the field supervisor for the PKL students and analyzes the progress of the system that will be created. Several discussions were held with service officers to perfect the system. the systems required by library service officers and users are; easy to access system, simple display system, cheap budget but according to needs, clear features so users don't need detailed explanations, system can be accessed online, speeds up service time, can be done by minimal staff, good communication between officers and students directly, scientific paper files are uploaded safely, data is stored well and is easy to browse.

After the end of the internship period, there are several developments that must be carried out so that the library coordinates with the SIM (Management Information System) Technical Implementation Unit of the Muhammadiyah University of Sukabumi to improve the system. Apart from that, the Sukabumi Muhammadiyah University Library also collaborates with LPPM (Institute for Research and Community Service) as verifier of plagiarism services.

After the OK3S system existed Students do not have to access various links like before the OK3S system, they only need one database link and the data is integrated with SIAK (Academic and Financial Information System) so that students only need to use the appropriate email recorded in SIAK to access OK3S. SIAK (Academic and Financial Information System) is a system that manages various kinds of data and information regarding students, including payments, lectures, transfers, releases and so on.

5. Effectiveness of implementation efforts

The effectiveness of implementation efforts is one important measure of success. Rather than simply reflecting innovation success, measures of implementation success assume that effective innovation is an integral part of successful implementation and should be reflected therein. According to Real and Poole (2005: 80), Edmondson, Bohmer, and Pisano (2001) explain that to assess the effectiveness of implementation, it can be assessed by how well the implementation stages have been carried out to provide convenience for users of the innovation in the future. In addition, Real and Poole (2005) show that evaluating the

effectiveness of implementing an innovation also involves assessing the ability to overcome barriers to implementation. The effectiveness of implementation efforts not only measures the success of the innovation itself, but also how the innovation is implemented successfully.

It is important to understand that an effective innovation will only be successful if it is implemented well. Therefore, assessing implementation effectiveness includes how well the implementation process was carried out to ensure that the innovation can be used easily by future users. In addition, assessing implementation effectiveness also involves evaluating the ability to overcome obstacles that may arise during the implementation process.

Based on the results of interviews and observations of researchers, in practice the Sukabumi Muhammadiyah University Library as a manager has gone through several stages. Namely the preparation stage, system development stage and OK3S system implementation stage. In the preparation stage, the head of the library carried out a joint analysis with the library staff then held an audience with the UMMI Informatics Engineering study program to get internship students and had a coordination meeting with UPT. UMMI SIM to enter the system development stage. Then the system development stage. At this stage, the system is adjusted to the needs of managers and users of the OK3S system. and there are several feature developments that have been adjusted to suit needs. After that, the implementation stage, in the implementation stage there are several obstacles faced by managers and users. That is:

a) Obstacle

From the results of interviews with managers and users of the OK3S system, it was found that the implementation of public service innovation through the OK3S (One Click Three Services) system at the Muhammadiyah University Sukabumi Library was not optimal due to several factors. One of the main obstacles identified was a poor network which resulted in access not being able to be opened and the storage system still using the cloud, resulting in quite burdensome monthly fees. As stated by N.8 on June 5, 2024 at 13.00:

"I have tried the OK3S system and thank God it is very easy once you understand it, but unfortunately the OK3S system is often inaccessible."

Also supported by a statement from the manager the researcher interviewed, namely N.6 on 04 June 2024 stating that:

"The obstacle felt by the OK3S system is that sometimes the network goes down and the OK3S system cannot be accessed. This was so disturbing that the service was stopped."

Based on the results of an interview with N.2 on June 7 2024 at 13.00 in the UPT.SIM room at Muhammadiyah University, Sukabumi, it was stated that:

"The cause of the network going down was due to a hack on the Sukabumi Muhammadiyah University network system so that everything could not be accessed. "Because OK3S is connected to SIAK, this means OK3S cannot be accessed either."

Based on the interview, the network was down and the OK3S system could not be accessed due to hackers from people who were not responsible for the Sukabumi Muhammadiyah University network system, which also had an impact on the OK3S system.

Apart from that, the obstacle felt by the management is that the OK3S system must be stored on a cloud server because the server owned by the library is inadequate, so the library is burdened with monthly usage fees. In accordance with statement N.1 on date 09 June 2024 at 16.00 WIB states that:

"The obstacle we feel is that the server still uses the cloud, so there is a monthly fee that has to be paid. "Meanwhile, the budget that the UMMI library has is still limited."

b) Efforts made

From the interviews that researchers have conducted, the OK3S (One Click Three Services) system manager concluded that several efforts must be made to make innovation implementation run optimally, namely, efforts made by OK3S system managers (*One Click Three Services*) Handling bad networks that prevent access from being opened is by coordinating with UPT. SIM as the implementation team is responsible for handling network system problems. Apart from that, the management also informs users via social media or with notification flyers explaining that the network is not good. Based on a statement from N.4, that is:

"When a bad network system occurs and results in OK3S being inaccessible, we always coordinate with UPT.SIM to find out what problems are occurring. And if repairs take a long time, we will inform students that the network is under repair."

Apart from that, as stated by N.1 that:

"Providing adequate local servers needs to be made to save OK3S so that the infrastructure can be fully controlled and reduces long-term operational costs. "Apart from that, it is also necessary to increase server security so that it is not easily attacked by cybercrime or cyber crimes and carry out periodic data backups to make it easier to access or synchronize when disruptions or problems occur in the system."

Based on the interview, efforts were made to reduce monthly operational costs, namely by purchasing infrastructure in the form of its own server. Meanwhile, to overcome a hacked network, it is necessary to increase security, and it is also necessary to back up data regularly to anticipate data loss if a system disruption occurs.

Closing

Conclusion

Based on the research results, the implementation of Public Service Innovation through the OK3S (One Click Three Services) System at the Muhammadiyah University Sukabumi Library has several important things that can be concluded. The OK3S system provides easy access and utilization of library services online, with the integration of three main services in one platform that can be accessed via various devices, thereby increasing the effectiveness, efficiency and administration of library services through better communication between managers and users as well as simplifying the administration process. This has had a positive impact on feedback from stakeholders with reduced complaints regarding previously slow and complicated service

processes. OK3S was developed with a collaboration system that is effective in reducing development costs and is integrated with the university's academic and financial information systems. However, the implementation of OK3S also faces several technical obstacles, such as network problems, operational costs, and system security, which need to be overcome to ensure optimization of the services provided to users.

Suggestion

From the results of the research concluded above, the researcher proposes several recommendations that can be input into the implementation of public service innovation through the OK3S (One Click Three Services) system at the Muhammadiyah University Sukabumi Library. Here are some of the suggestions put forward:

Practical Aspects

Based on the conclusions above, further efforts are needed to provide better understanding and access to the OK3S (One Click Three Services) system innovation to all stakeholders. In particular, it is necessary to increase socialization to users by the management regarding the system, apart from that there is also a need to add a video tutorial feature in addition to the written guidelines on the OK3S page to help users apply it.

Theoretical Aspects

Researchers suggest conducting further research regarding the Implementation of Public Service Innovation through the OK3S (One Click Three Services) System at the Muhammadiyah University Sukabumi Library using other variables besides the Real and Poole Innovation Implementation theory, namely; Use, Performance, User Attitudes and Beliefs, Integration into the Organization, Effectiveness of Implementation Effort in the hope of obtaining detailed and expanding information scientific study and understanding.

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